

Sulfur in diamond and its effect on the creation of nitrogen-vacancy defect from *ab initio* simulationsNima Ghafari Cherati

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The negatively charged nitrogen-vacancy (NV) center is one of the most significant and widely studied defects in diamond that plays a prominent role in quantum technologies. The precise engineering of the location and concentration of NV centers is of great importance in quantum technology applications. To this end, irradiation techniques such as nitrogen-molecule ion implantation are applied. Recent studies have reported enhanced NV center creation and activation efficiencies introduced by nitrogen molecule ion implantation in doped diamond layers, where the maximum creation efficiency at $\sim 75\%$ has been achieved in sulfur-doped layers. However, the microscopic mechanisms behind these observations and the limits of the efficiencies are far from understood. In this study, we employ hybrid density-functional-theory calculations to compute the formation energies, charge transition levels, and the magneto-optical properties of various sulfur defects in diamond where we also consider the interaction of sulfur and hydrogen in chemical vapor-deposited diamond layers. Our results imply that the competition between the donor substitutional sulfur and the hyperdeep acceptor sulfur-vacancy complex is an important limiting factor on the creation efficiency of the NV center in diamond. However, both species are able to trap interstitial hydrogen from diamond, which favorably mediates the creation of NV centers in chemical vapor-deposited diamond layers.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been an ever-growing interest in quantum technologies that are based on the physical realization of controllable two-level quantum mechanical systems, *viz.*, quantum bits or qubits. Defect spins in solids have emerged as a promising platform among various solutions to this end [1]. The negatively charged nitrogen-vacancy (NV) center in diamond with electron spin $S = 1$ stands out within the family of solid-state defect qubits, notable for its long spin coherence times at room temperature [2–5]. Quantum technology applications demand the precise placement of the qubits in a scalable manner. Motivated by the success of *n*-type doping of silicon in the semiconductor industry by dopant implantation, the target defect qubits in solids can also be introduced by ion implantation, which allows for controlled defect concentrations. Specifically, nitrogen molecule ions are typically implanted into pure chemical vapor-deposited (CVD) diamond (e.g., Ref. [6]) and then annealing is applied to create NV defects by the combination of the immobile substitutional nitrogen and the mobile vacancy. The substitutional nitrogen in diamond acts as a donor and contributes an electron to the NV defect. Thus, the implanted nitrogen serves

a dual role in the creation of the negatively charged NV defect in diamond: It not only facilitates the creation of the NV defect but also donates an electron to the NV defect. The creation efficiency (i.e., the ratio of successfully created negatively charged NV defect per number of nitrogen molecule ions) of this method is $\sim 1\%$ [6]. *Ab initio* calculations showed [7] that the formation of a divacancy, involving two vacancies, is more probable than the combination of the substitutional nitrogen (N_s) and a vacancy (V). As a result, vacancy aggregates are more likely to form than NV defects, which could explain the low creation efficiency of NV centers with this method.

Recently, a major breakthrough has been made in the creation efficiency of NV centers by doping diamond with specific elements prior to nitrogen molecule ion implantation [8]. In particular, predoping CVD diamond with phosphorus, oxygen, and sulfur has resulted in creation yields of 57.9%, 69.3%, and 75.3%, respectively. Among those, sulfur doped diamond not only yields the highest creation efficiency of the NV centers but also provides the longest spin coherence times. The remarkable enhancement in NV center creation efficiency has been explained by the donor nature of the dopants, which negatively charge the vacancies, thus preventing vacancy aggregation and promoting the formation of NV centers, particularly when the N_s is positively charged [8].

Indeed, substitutional phosphorus (P_s) is a well-established *n*-type dopant in diamond [9–16], with its donor level located 0.6 eV below the conduction band minimum ($E_c - 0.6$ eV). In contrast, the role of oxygen in diamond remains less well

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established. In our previous theoretical study with hybrid density functional supercell calculations, we found [17] that substitutional oxygen (O_s) exhibits single and double donor levels at $E_c - 3.2$ eV and $E_c - 4.9$ eV, respectively, which are still to be confirmed in experiments. The same study predicted that O_s is the most stable oxygen-related defect, although oxygen forms a complex with vacancies, i.e., oxygen-vacancy (OV) defect, when mobile vacancies are available in diamond. The OV defect is amphoteric, possessing both deep donor and acceptor levels in the diamond band gap. In turn, the behavior of sulfur in diamond is even less understood experimentally. A theoretical study reported the donor level of substitutional sulfur (S_s) at $E_c - 0.79$ eV [18], suggesting a relatively shallow donor character. However, this study relied on semilocal density-functional-theory (DFT) calculations which significantly underestimate the band gap of diamond. Therefore, the position of the donor level of S_s needs to be revisited. More recent DFT calculations have yielded the donor level at $E_c - 1.6$ eV using a method which accurately reproduces the diamond band gap [19]. Another theoretical study, also based on semilocal DFT, considered a complex of sulfur and vacancy (SV) defect [20]. They concluded that sulfur remains at the substitutional site within the SV defect [20], similar to the OV defect mentioned above [17]. This is surprising, as the sulfur atom is relatively large and might be expected to relax to the interstitial site in the complex. Indeed, semilocal DFT calculations showed that sulfur occupies the bond-center interstitial site in the SV defect, resulting in a D_{3d} symmetry configuration [21,22]. This configuration, also known as the “split-vacancy,” may be seen as a divacancy, where a pair of adjacent vacancies is connected by an interstitial dopant atom. The split-vacancy configuration also appears for the group-IV–vacancy color centers in diamond [23]. It can be denoted as VSV for sulfur dopant or VSiV for silicon dopant, referring to the dopant’s position in the diamond lattice. However, since the SiV label has been rather spread in the literature, we also prefer to use it here for sulfur in the SV defect. Furthermore, the same semilocal DFT calculations [22] also predicted that the most stable interstitial sulfur configuration has significantly higher formation energy (~ 7 eV) than substitutional sulfur (S_s), while the SV defect is favored over the S_s by ~ 4 eV in the neutral charge state. Additionally, they attributed [22] the sulfur-related W31 electron spin resonance center [24] to the negatively charged SV defect of electron spin $S = 1/2$, based on both the calculated and observed hyperfine signals of ^{33}S ($I = 3/2$) and ^{13}C ($I = 1/2$) nuclear spins. However, we note that the relative stability of these defects as a function of the Fermi level cannot be accurately predicted in these calculations because of the inherent band-gap error in semilocal density functionals.

The limited understanding of the relationship between the donor levels of dopants and the creation efficiency of the NV center, coupled with the contradicting theoretical results on sulfur defects in diamond, motivated us to carry out a systematic and thorough investigation of sulfur defects in diamond using hybrid density-functional-theory calculations. We consider a variety of basic defects, including interstitial and substitutional sulfur defects as well as sulfur-vacancy complexes. Given that dopants and nitrogen were implanted into CVD diamond within tens of nanometers in depth in the

key experimental study [8], the diamond layers are likely to contain interstitial hydrogen atoms. Therefore, we also studied the interaction of hydrogen with the selected sulfur-related defects. The methodology used to accurately predict the defect properties is detailed in Sec. II. The results on the considered defects are reported in Sec. III, where we also discuss their implications on the creation efficiency of NV centers in diamond. Finally, we summarize our findings and conclusions in Sec. IV.

II. METHODOLOGY

The calculations were performed using *ab initio* DFT, implemented in Vienna *Ab initio* Simulation Package (VASP) [25] within the projector-augmented-wave (PAW) [26] method. A plane-wave basis with a cutoff energy of 450 eV was employed. Unlike in the previous studies on sulfur defects, which used the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) functional [27] to optimize the structure and obtain the electronic structure, we employed the screened hybrid density functional of Heyd, Scuseria, and Ernzerhof (HSE), with using the proposed mixing (0.25) and screening (0.2 $1/\text{\AA}$) parameters for solids, labeled as HSE06 [28]. This approach can accurately reproduce the experimental band gap of diamond and defect levels in the gap with a typical accuracy of 0.1 eV [29]. This could be achieved because of the piecewise linearity condition, i.e., the ground-state total energy as a function of electron number is nearly linear on electron occupation with integer electron numbers that is fulfilled both to the band edges (see a recent study in Ref. [30]) and the defect states inside the band gap [29].

The defects were created in a $4 \times 4 \times 4$ cubic 512-atom supercell. With this supercell size, accurate results can be achieved by sampling the Brillouin zone at the Γ point. The structural relaxation was performed until reaching the convergence thresholds for total energy and ionic forces of 10^{-5} eV and 10^{-3} eV/ \AA , respectively. The optimized lattice constants of $a_{\text{HSE06}} = 3.544$ \AA were obtained for the unit cell.

The relative stability of various defects was evaluated based on the calculated formation energies. Specifically, we computed the formation energy E_f^q for defects in a charge state q as follows [31]:

$$E_f^q = E_{\text{tot}}^q - E_{\text{bulk}} - \sum_i n_i \mu_i + qE_{\text{Fermi}} + E_{\text{corr}}^q, \quad (1)$$

where E_{tot}^q and E_{bulk} are the total energies of the defective and pristine diamond, respectively; μ_i is the chemical potential for each atom type, i ; while n_i is a number of added ($n_i > 0$) or removed ($n_i < 0$) atoms relative to the bulk system. E_{Fermi} is the Fermi level, referenced to the valence band maximum (E_v). E_{corr}^q is a correction term for the total energies of charged supercells [32]. In our study, defective supercells may contain carbon, sulfur, and hydrogen atoms. The chemical potential of carbon was calculated from diamond reference as the total energy per carbon atom. For defining the sulfur chemical potential we used the total energy of a S_8 crystal per sulfur atom as a reference. Finally, the hydrogen chemical potential was calculated from a slab model of (001)-(2 \times 1) reconstructed and hydrogen-terminated diamond surface as we described in our previous work [7].

The charge transition level of a given defect can be defined as $E_{\text{Fermi}}(q1|q2) \equiv E_f^{q2} = E_f^{q1}$ which leads to the following equation,

$$E_{\text{Fermi}}(q1|q2) = [(E_{\text{tot}}^{q2} + E_{\text{corr}}^{q2}) - (E_{\text{tot}}^{q1} + E_{\text{corr}}^{q1})]/(q1 - q2), \quad (2)$$

where E_{Fermi} is given with respect to E_v . We note that the charge transition levels also yield the respective photoionization threshold energies. For instance, the electron from the occupied defect level may be promoted to the conduction band by illumination when the frequency of the photon can bridge the energy gap between the total energy of the photoionized excited state with the electron in the conduction band minimum and the total energy of the ground state. Therefore, the donor charge transition levels are referenced to E_c because these values provide the photoionization threshold energies. On the other hand, the electrons from the valence band maximum or deeper valence bands may be promoted to the empty defect level in the band gap by illumination. Thus, the acceptor charge transition levels are referenced to E_v by providing again the photoionization threshold energies for this process.

We also studied the defect chemistry in diamond, i.e., the feasibility of defect complexation from isolated species, where we assume at least one of the constituents of the complex to be mobile at the given annealing temperature. By comparing the formation energies of the isolated defects (A and B) with that of the complex (AB), the binding energy is defined as

$$E_b = E_A^f + E_B^f - E_{AB}^f. \quad (3)$$

A positive value of the binding energy means that the complex formation is favorable from the thermodynamic point of view in this definition, although configurational entropy may also play a role [33]. It is important to note that the formation energy generally depends on the position of the Fermi level in the fundamental band gap. At a given Fermi level, A and B defects may exist in q_A and q_B charge states. If the signs of q_A and q_B are the same, then the constituent defects repel each other, thus we assume that the complex does not form because of kinetic reasons. On the other hand, if the signs of q_A and q_B are the opposite, then the defects will attract each other which could mediate the formation of the complex if the calculated $E_b > 0$. Finally, the total charge should be conserved in the defect reaction. As a consequence, if $q_{\text{diff}} \equiv q_{AB} - (q_A + q_B) > 0$ at the given Fermi level and the complex formation is favorable, then a hole (h^+) will be ejected. If $q_{\text{diff}} < 0$ and the complex formation is favorable, then an electron (e^-) will be ejected in the process.

We calculate the hyperfine tensor of the paramagnetic defects with the optimized geometry which can provide a fingerprint of the defects in electron spin resonance measurements of diamond where the electron spin may interact with the proximate nuclear spins. With considering the relativistic effects, the hyperfine tensor of the nucleus consists of the Fermi-contact term and the dipole-dipole term which is given

as

$$A_{ij}^I = \frac{1}{2S} \int n_s(r) \gamma_I \gamma_e \hbar^2 \left[\left(\frac{8\pi}{3} \delta(r) \right) + \left(\frac{3x_i x_j}{r^5} - \frac{\delta_{ij}}{r^3} \right) \right] d^3 r, \quad (4)$$

where $n_s(r)$ is the spin density of the spin state S , γ_I is the nuclear Bohr magneton of nucleus I , and γ_e is the electron Bohr magneton. The Fermi-contact term is proportional to the spin density localized at the place of the nucleus which may be dominant compared to the dipole-dipole term when the spin density is strongly localized around the ions in the core of the defect. We calculate the hyperfine tensor and diagonalize it to obtain hyperfine constants, which can be directly compared with experimental data. The Fermi-contact and the dipole-dipole terms are simply derived from the trace of the hyperfine tensors. The ratio of the Fermi-contact and dipole-dipole terms characterizes the shape of the spin density. We note that Eq. (4) is modified within PAW formalism and the core spin polarization correction should be added for yielding accurate hyperfine tensors, in particular, for ^{13}C isotopes with $I = 1/2$ spins [34].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section is split into two main parts. In part one, we study the sulfur defects in diamond. In part two, we discuss the impact of sulfur defects on the creation efficiency of the NV center introduced by nitrogen molecular ion implantation. We also compare the impacts of oxygen defects with those of the sulfur defects on this creation efficiency. The results of oxygen, nitrogen, and intrinsic defects required for the discussion are taken from previous studies. As these two parts are tightly intertwined, we decided to place them into the same section.

A. Overview on the considered sulfur defects

The most elemental sulfur defects are the interstitial, S_i , substitutional, S_s , and the complex with a vacancy, SV. In the context of the main goal of our study, it is important to consider that many vacancies are generated during implantation. The combination of an additional vacancy with the SV defect may lead to the formation of a larger complex, SVV. Therefore, we also consider SVV defect where this label indicates removal of a nearby carbon atom with the dangling bond from the core of the split-vacancy SV defect. In the key experiments [8] that motivated our study, the dopant implantation and the subsequent nitrogen molecular ion implantation were carried out into CVD diamond layers to a depth of a few tens of nanometers. The use of CVD layers as starting materials for generating NV centers is very general, since ultrahigh purity diamond layers can only be prepared by the chemical vapor deposition method. This technique employs atomic hydrogen, which may diffuse into the diamond. Thus, it can be assumed that interstitial hydrogen (H_i) may exist in the top layers of CVD diamonds. These H_i s may interact with sulfur defects and other defects created by implantation. Specifically, we consider the complexes of hydrogen with S_s and sulfur-vacancy defects, which we label SH, SVH, and SVVH, respectively. We note that larger hydrogen-related

FIG. 1. Electronic structure for the ground states of the neutral defects using HSE06 functional. Kohn–Sham levels are represented by spin-up (\uparrow) and spin-down (\downarrow). The valence band (VB) and conduction band (CB) are depicted in cyan and orange, respectively. It is important to note that while the SVH structure is optimized in C_1 symmetry, the wave functions follow C_{1h} symmetry. Therefore, we have labeled the states using C_{1h} symmetry labels.

complexes may also occur, e.g., silicon-vacancy-hydrogen complexes [35,36] but considering these complexes with multiple hydrogen atoms is beyond the scope of this study.

We first show the electronic structure of the considered neutral defect species for the most stable configurations in Fig. 1. As shown, all the considered defects introduce multiple defect levels into the fundamental band gap of diamond. We calculated the formation energies for the most stable configurations, which also revealed their stable charge states as a function of the Fermi level. The results are plotted in the left panel of Fig. 2. In the right panel of Fig. 2, we also plot the formation energies of the related oxygen and nitrogen defects,

which will be important in the discussion of the creation efficiency of NV centers in doped diamond.

B. Interstitial sulfur defects

Different sites within diamond may host sulfur as an interstitial defect. A previous DFT study has already considered the possible configurations of sulfur interstitial [22], which we use as a guideline in this work. More specifically, they found that S_i is least stable at the empty T and H sites of the diamond lattice but is more stable in a distorted [001] split-interstitial position [22]. Furthermore, it was shown [22] that this configuration transforms into the $S_s + C_i$ configuration with a

FIG. 2. Formation energy of the defects as a function of the position of the Fermi level. E_v is aligned to zero for the sake of simplicity. E_c is at 5.4 eV. Left panel: sulfur-related defects. Right panel: oxygen and nitrogen defects where the data are extracted from Refs. [7,17].

FIG. 3. Geometry of optimized interstitial sulfur configurations in the order of hierarchy. (a) $S + I$, (b) $(S-C)_C$, (c) H site, and (d) T site. S and C atoms are depicted as yellow and dark spheres, respectively.

relatively low barrier energy, where C_i is a self-interstitial carbon atom near S_s in a split-interstitial position. The $S_s + C_i$ complex then becomes the most stable configuration of the interstitial sulfur. This type of complex formation is well known for the boron interstitial in silicon and is often labeled as $B + I$ complex, where “I” denotes the self-interstitial atom (see, e.g., Ref. [37]). By following this syntax, the most stable interstitial sulfur may be labeled as $S + I$ in diamond. We note that the relative stability of defects can depend on the choice of density functional, as the total energy depends on the defect level positions in the gap. The main reason behind this phenomenon is that the occupied defect levels with underestimated band gap in (semi)local DFT calculations can shift significantly in hybrid DFT calculations with an enlarged band gap. Therefore, it is useful to revisit the relative stability of interstitial sulfur configurations with hybrid DFT calculations. We found that the hierarchy of stabilities agrees well with the (semi) local DFT results, with the $S + I$ configuration being the most stable interstitial sulfur defect. The distorted [001] split-interstitial configuration follows by 2.09 eV, while the H and T sites exhibit significantly higher total energies (see Fig. 3).

The electronic structure of the most stable interstitial sulfur defect in the ground state is depicted in Fig. 1. We find this defect to have a C_{1h} (C_s) symmetry with a closed-shell singlet ground state and three localized states in the fundamental band gap. The $1a'$ and $1a''$ orbitals are fully occupied, while the $2a''$ orbital is empty. The defect can be ionized and we calculated the respective charge transition levels.

C. Substitutional sulfur

By substituting carbon with sulfur, two extra electrons are provided into the lattice. Our calculation revealed that the substitutional sulfur, S_s , can exist in doubly positive, singly positive, and neutral charge states depending on the position of the Fermi level.

In the neutral charge state, the two extra electrons occupy a triple degenerate t_2 level in the band gap. This creates a Jahn-Teller unstable system. We find that the C_{2v} distortion represents the most stable structure, followed by a C_{3v} distorted structure with spin-singlet ground state. This result is corroborated by recent molecular dynamics calculations [19]. We also note that similar Jahn-Teller behavior was observed for substitutional nickel defect in diamond [38].

The electronic structure of the neutral S_s in the ground state is depicted in Fig. 1. This defect, which has a spin-singlet

ground state, exhibits a fully occupied a_1 and an empty b_1 level. Both the fully symmetric a_1 and the asymmetric b_1 orbitals are localized on the p orbitals of sulfur, with additional contributions from the nearest carbon atoms.

In the single-positive-charge state, a single electron occupies the triple degenerate t_2 level, which again leads to a Jahn-Teller unstable configuration. We find that the C_{3v} geometry is the most stable configuration with $S = 1/2$ ground state. However, in the $(2+)$ charge state, the defect remains in tetrahedral symmetry (see Fig. 4) with spin-singlet ground state.

Previous calculations from Wang *et al.* [18] reported the $(+|0)$ donor level at $E_c - 0.79$ eV. However, our calculations predict this charge transition level at $E_c - 1.6$ eV which agrees well with the result of a recent work [19]. The calculated second donor level, $(2+|+)$, is located at $E_c - 2.9$ eV.

The $S_s(+)$ defect is paramagnetic, which can be detected by electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy. Indeed, a sulfur-related $S = 1/2$ EPR center, labeled as W31 center [24], was observed with trigonal symmetry in diamond. The chemical identification of W31 was based on the relative intensity of the hyperfine lines corresponding to the 0.7% natural abundance of ^{33}S , which has a nuclear spin $I = 3/2$.

Given that $S_s(+)$ has trigonal symmetry, it could have been associated with the W31 EPR center. The calculated spin density of $S_s(+)$ defect is depicted in Fig. 5. The spin density is distributed around the carbon atoms neighboring the sulfur dopant, where ^{13}C isotope (with nuclear spin $I = 1/2$ and 1.1% natural abundance) may also appear as hyperfine satellite lines in the EPR spectrum. Due to the C_{3v} symmetry, the spin density and the hyperfine constants on the three carbon atoms (C_1 , C_2 , and C_3 in Fig. 5) are identical. The observed

FIG. 4. Geometry of optimized sulfur substitutional defect in various charge states. The $(2+)$ state is isovalent with carbon resulting in T_d symmetry. Additional electrons distort the geometry because of Jahn-Teller distortion. S and C atoms are defined as yellow and dark spheres, respectively.

FIG. 5. Spin-density distribution around the core of the $S_s(+)$ defect (a) side and (b) top view of $(1\bar{1}0)$ plane. S and C atoms are shown by yellow and dark spheres, respectively. The hyperfine constants for the atoms labeled here are given in Table I. Yellow lobes represent a positive isovalues of the calculated spin density with isosurface value at 0.008 \AA^{-3} .

and computed hyperfine constants are provided in Table I. It becomes apparent that the calculated hyperfine constants for ^{33}S are much smaller than the values observed for the W31 center, which rules out the $S_s(+)$ defect as a likely candidate for this center. Note that these results are consistent with a previous DFT study [22].

D. Sulfur-vacancy defect

During the implantation process, a large number of vacancies are created in the diamond lattice. Typically, thermal annealing is applied to remedy the crystalline structure of diamond, which induces mobility of the vacancies at certain temperatures. A single or multiple mobile vacancies may combine with the substitutional sulfur and form sulfur-vacancy complexes. The simplest of these complexes involves the pairing of a single vacancy with sulfur, which we label as SV defect.

TABLE I. Hyperfine tensors for the W31 EPR center (MHz) (experimental data are taken from Ref. [24]) and the $SV(-)$ and $S_s(+)$ defects calculated by HSE06 functional in diamond. The atom labels are shown in Fig. 7.

Atom	n	A_{\parallel}	A_{\perp}	$A_{\parallel}(\theta, \phi)$
W31	$S = 1/2$			
S	1	1029.0	1033.7	54.7, 45
C ₁	4	70.6	45.1	61, -135
C ₂	6	14.9	9.8	$\langle 111 \rangle$
C ₃	12	4.8	4.8	Isotropic
$SV(-)$	$S = 1/2$			
S	1	1120.7	1135.8	54.7, 45
C ₁	6	69.4	42.2	59.2, -135
C ₂	12	-4.5	-3.5	54.1, -42.2
C ₃	6	15.2	8.6	47.3, 45
C ₄	6	7	5.5	174.7, -135.2
C ₅	12	4.3	3.0	55.1, 49.7
C ₆	6	11.4	8.1	53.6, -135.0
C ₇	6	5.7	4.2	59.3, 45
$S_s(+)$	$S = 1/2$			
S	1	136.9	27.5	54.7, 45
C ₍₁₋₃₎	3	70.7	52.2	36, -135
C ₄	1	218.3	167	54.7, 45

FIG. 6. The optimized geometry of sulfur-vacancy complexes. (a) SV defect and (b) SVV defect. S and C atoms are illustrated as yellow and dark spheres, respectively. The dashed spheres represent the vacancies.

Our calculations show that sulfur adjacent to a vacancy relaxes to the interstitial site near the vacancy, at the inversion point of the diamond lattice (the “split-interstitial” position), where it adopts a D_{3d} symmetry. In turn, the on-site SV configuration, which exhibits C_{3v} symmetry, lies about 2.64 eV higher in energy than the most stable D_{3d} configuration [see Fig. 6(a)].

In the SV defect, six carbon dangling bonds are created, with sulfur providing six electrons to the lattice. The six dangling bonds give rise to the a_{2u} , e_u , e_g , and a_{1g} defect levels, where the e_u and e_g are double degenerate, whereas sulfur also creates a deep a_{1g} level. In total, 12 electrons occupy the a_{1g} , a_{2u} , e_u , and e_g levels, whereas the upper a_{1g} level remains empty in the neutral charge state. Among these, the fully occupied e_g level appears just above the valence band maximum, whereas the empty a_{1g} level lies in the upper half of the band gap. Due to the parity selection rule, optical transitions between the e_g and a_{1g} are forbidden, making this defect optically inactive.

Furthermore, on the charge-state transition, the empty a_{1g} level may be filled with either one or two electrons. We find that the $SV(-)$ defect is stable when the Fermi level lies between $E_v + 4.0 \text{ eV}$ and $E_v + 4.5 \text{ eV}$ (see Fig. 2). If sulfur donors remain in the diamond lattice after sulfur implantation, then they may stabilize $SV(-)$ with donating an electron towards the SV defect.

The $SV(-)$ is a paramagnetic defect with a ground state of spin $S = 1/2$. To characterize its magnetic properties, we calculated both the spin-density and hyperfine tensors. The spin density is shown in Fig. 7. To distinguish between atoms in different neighbor shells, we assigned unique colors to the atoms from the second to the seventh nearest-neighbor shells. Atoms sharing the same color are equivalent, having identical hyperfine constants. As shown in Fig. 7, the first through seventh nearest-neighbor shells contain 6, 12, 6, 6, 12, 6, and 6 equivalent carbon atoms, respectively, consistent with the D_{3d} symmetry of the defect. The respective hyperfine constants for these atoms are provided in Table I, along with their multiplicities (n).

Superhyperfine satellites are observed alongside the main hyperfine splitting from the ^{33}S in the W31 EPR center [24]. These satellites can be attributed to hyperfine coupling with ^{13}C nuclear spins. The study identified 4 ^{13}C atoms in the first shell, 6 in the second shell, and 12 in the third shell, all symmetrically equivalent within their respective shells.

FIG. 7. Spin-density distribution around the core of the SV(−) defect with side view respect to (110) plane. S and C atoms are shown by yellow and dark spheres, respectively. For the second, third, fourth, fifth, and sixth nearest neighbors, we changed the carbon atoms color to red, blue, green, pink, orange, and white, respectively. The hyperfine constants for the atoms labeled here are given in Table I. Yellow lobes represent positive isovalues of the calculated spin density with isosurface value at 0.007 \AA^{-3} .

In a later theoretical study [22], the W31 EPR center was associated with the SV(−) defect, with the authors concluding that the number of equivalent ^{13}C atoms in the first shell is 6.

To simulate the EPR spectrum in the X band, we used the calculated hyperfine tensors, focusing specifically on the ^{13}C superhyperfine satellites (depicted by the red curve in Fig. 8). To this end, we employed the EASYSOFT code [39]. Unfortunately, the direct comparison with the observed EPR spectrum is extremely difficult because the quality of the plot, reported in Ref. [24] is barely reproducible and we were unable to find any other publications with showing the spectrum of the W31 EPR center. Therefore, we rather used the spin Hamiltonian, which was fitted to the experimental data as given in Ref. [24] (e.g., hyperfine tensors and multiplicity of ^{13}C spins), to generate a derived EPR spectrum (blue curve in Fig. 8).

Based on the good agreement between the experimental and simulated spectra, we infer that the W31 EPR center is associated with the SV(−) defect which agrees with the result of a previous study [22]. To further support this assignment, the EPR spectrum of the W31 center should be revisited by carefully recording the spectrum in the region of the main electron spin transition in order to accurately obtain the

FIG. 8. Simulated EPR spectrum for SV(−) defect (red curve) and the EPR spectrum as derived from the spin Hamiltonian of the W31 EPR center (blue curve) from Ref. [24]. The hyperfine splitting from ^{33}S is not shown here. The respective ^{13}C hyperfine tensors are listed in Table I.

respective relative intensity between the main EPR line and the hyperfine satellites.

In the experimental study, the W31 EPR center was found in Type 1b diamond [24] which contains a relatively high concentration of nitrogen impurities. However, the mechanism by which sulfur was incorporated into the diamond in that study remains unclear [24]. Both substitutional nitrogen (N_s) and sulfur may act as donors (see Fig. 2) that can provide an electron towards the SV defect to form SV(−). If S_s defects coexist with isolated vacancies in the sample, then annealing may initiate the formation of SV complex when mobile vacancies are trapped by the S_s .

We further proceed by studying the trapping mechanism of a vacancy by the S_s through *ab initio* calculations. To this end, the vacancy was placed at the fourth-neighbor shell along the (110) plane (labeled as SCCCV), and we used (100) direction as a configuration coordinate to map the adiabatic potential energy surface as the vacancy approaches the S_s . The resulting configurations were labeled as SCCV and SCV, and the final configuration was the SV defect as depicted in Fig. 9.

Our calculations reveal that the diffusion barrier energy reduces successively as the vacancy approaches the S_s . The calculated highest diffusion barrier energy almost coincides with the value for the diffusion of the neutral vacancies in diamond (2.8 eV) using the HSE06 functional [7]. These results imply that the mobile vacancy is effectively trapped by the S_s and the SV defect can be readily formed. The main driving forces behind the formation of the complex are the attractive strain field towards the vacancies, generated by the S_s , as well as the charge transfer between the species where the electron flows from the S_s towards the vacancy.

The large energy gain ($\approx 8 \text{ eV}$) in the formation of the complex can be understood as the elimination of the high-energy dangling bonds of the vacancy and the reduction in local strain around the SV defect relative to the S_s . In the most stable split-vacancy configuration of the SV defect, the six dangling bonds interact strongly with the sulfur ion, as we already discussed in our analysis of the electronic structure of the SV defect.

We note that we performed analogous calculations for the complex formation between oxygen and vacancy in a previous study [40]. In that work, we found a metastable OCCV configuration [40], using the same labeling scheme for the oxygen complex as we did for the sulfur complex. A similar metastable structure was also found for complexes of two vacancies, VCCV [41]. However, the sulfur-vacancy complexes do not follow this pattern. Specifically, the SCCV has a higher formation energy than the SCV defect. We attribute this difference to the large strain field generated by the S_s , which stabilizes the SCV relative to the SCCV. In contrast, no large strain field is present for the O_s or the vacancy defect, making their configurations behave differently.

E. Sulfur-vacancy-vacancy defect

In sulfur-implanted samples, multiple vacancies are formed, leading to the potential trapping of another vacancy by the SV defect, thereby creating the SVV complex. Therefore, we considered the SVV defect in our study where

FIG. 9. Geometry of the defects after optimization along $[110]$ mirror plane for SV, SCV, SCCV, and SCCC. S and C atoms are yellow and dark spheres, respectively. The diffusion barrier energy are $E_{b1} = 0.87$ eV, $E_{b2} = 2.70$ eV, and $E_{b3} = 2.77$ eV.

the optimized structure of the neutral defect is depicted in Fig. 6(b).

Four defect levels appear in the band gap due to the SVV (see Fig. 1). The a' and a'' occupied levels are mainly localized on the carbon dangling bonds, while the empty ones are the carbon-sulfur antibonding orbitals mixed with the carbon-centered orbitals at the second vacancy site farther from the sulfur ion. As the a' and a'' levels are close in energy, a high-spin state $S = 1$ is stabilized in the neutral charge state. The occupied and empty defect levels in the gap indicate that SVV may occur in various charge states. Indeed, we find that $(+)$, (0) , $(-)$, and $(2-)$ charge states can exist, while the $(-)$ state of $S = 1/2$ spans a wide range of the Fermi energies in the upper half of the band gap (see Fig. 2).

In both the neutral and negative charge states, the SVV defect is paramagnetic, with the total spin values of $S = 1$ and $S = 1/2$, respectively. The calculated spin density in the negative charge state is shown in Fig. 10, where we labeled

the atoms for which the hyperfine tensors are provided in Table II. In the neutral charge state, the spin density is mostly distributed over the C_{1-3} atoms. Due to the C_{1h} symmetry, the spin density (and consequently hyperfine constants) on the C_2 and C_3 atoms (similarly on C_4 and C_5 and on C_6 and C_7 for the negative charge state) are identical. In the neutral charge state, a marginal spin density is observed on the sulfur atom; instead, the spin is predominantly localized on the sp^3 hybridized dangling bonds of the C_{1-3} carbon atoms. In contrast, on the introduction of an additional electron to form the SVV $(-)$, a redistribution of spin density occurs, which results in significant spin localization on the sulfur atom and its four adjacent carbon atoms.

FIG. 10. Spin-density distribution around the core of the SVV $(-)$ defect with two different views: (a) side and (b) top view of $(1\bar{1}0)$ plane. S and C atoms are shown by yellow and dark spheres, respectively. The hyperfine constants for the atoms labeled here are given in Table I. Yellow lobes represent positive isovalues while blue lobes represent negative isovalues of the calculated spin density with an isosurface value at 0.01 \AA^{-3} .

TABLE II. Hyperfine constants (A_{xx} , A_{yy} , and A_{zz}) of the sulfur atom and the nearest-neighbor atoms for the neutral and negatively charged SVV defects. The atom labels are shown in Fig. 10.

Atom	A_{xx} (MHz)	A_{yy} (MHz)	A_{zz} (MHz)
SVV(0)	$S = 1/2$		
S	50.1		56.3
C_1	86.6	49.3	173.7
C_{2-3}	85.2	84.6	159.4
SVV $(-)$	$S = 1$		
S	-374.1	-372.4	-419.5
C_1	162.8	161.8	264.7
C_{2-3}	194.7	194.3	354.4
C_{4-5}	-50.9	-49.2	-83.4
C_{6-7}	-33.1	-29.4	-56.9

FIG. 11. The optimized geometry of (a) SH, (b) SVH, (c) SVVH complexes. S, H, and C atoms are illustrated as yellow, blue, and dark spheres, respectively.

F. Complexes of hydrogen and substitutional sulfur

To proceed, we considered the complexes of hydrogen with sulfur defects which may occur in CVD diamonds. First, we present the results on the complex of hydrogen and substitutional sulfur, i.e., the SH defect. SH defects were previously studied by semilocal DFT calculations, and it was concluded that the most stable SH defect acts as a shallow donor [42].

With substitutional sulfur, the hydrogen interstitial atom (H_i) can be positioned either at the antibonding or bond-centered site. Our calculations show that the antibonding site is the most stable configuration for the SH defect [see Fig. 11(a)], while the bond-centered position is 0.91 eV higher in energy. This finding is consistent with the results of previous calculations [42,43]. This defect with an almost C_{1h} symmetry and a doublet ground state $S = 1/2$ generates three levels in the band gap (see Fig. 1), with the spin density depicted in Fig. 12. We further calculated the hyperfine tensors for the ^1H , ^{13}C , and ^{33}S nuclei with natural abundance 99.98%, 1.1%, and 0.75%, respectively. Because of the C_{1h} symmetry, the spin density and the hyperfine constants on the C_1 and C_2 atoms are identical. The hyperfine constants are presented in Table III.

Previous semilocal DFT calculations predicted [42] that the SH defect has a relatively shallow donor level at $E_c - 0.61$ eV. However, semilocal DFT methods underestimate the fundamental band gap of diamond by about 1 eV which makes this prediction ambiguous. Indeed, our HSE06 calculations result in the donor level at $E_c - 1.2$ eV which is relatively deep, though it is a shallower donor than the S_s (see Fig. 2).

FIG. 12. Spin-density distribution around the core of the SH defect with two different views: (a) side and (b) top view of $(1\bar{1}0)$ plane. S and C atoms are shown by yellow and dark spheres, respectively. The hyperfine constants for the atoms labeled here are given in Table III. Yellow lobes represent a positive isovalues and blue lobes present a negative isovalues in the calculated spin density with an isosurface value at 0.009 \AA^{-3} .

TABLE III. Hyperfine constants (A_{xx} , A_{yy} , and A_{zz}) for the nearest-neighbor atoms for the neutral SH defect. The atom labels are shown in Fig. 12.

Atom	A_{xx} (MHz)	A_{yy} (MHz)	A_{zz} (MHz)
S	-27.5	-20.0	57.3
H	-11.4	-7.1	-13.9
C_{1-2}	150.9	149.8	183.9
C_3	-7.0	-5.7	-8.9

G. Complexes of hydrogen and sulfur-vacancy defects

1. Sulfur-vacancy-hydrogen complex

The diffusing hydrogen interstitial may also be trapped by the SV defect, which is the most stable sulfur-related defect in diamond. By adding one hydrogen to the SV defect, one of the sulfur-carbon bonds breaks, and the system adopts a C_{1h} symmetry [see Fig. 11(b)]. As a result, the e_u level splits into a' and a'' levels (see Fig. 1). The neutral charge state of the SVH defect is stable, when the Fermi level is located in the lower half of the band gap, whereas the negative charge state is the most stable for the Fermi level in the upper half of the band gap.

The neutral charge state of the SVH defect has an odd number of electrons with a ground state $S = 1/2$, with strong spin-density localization on the sulfur atom (see Fig. 13). As a consequence, the SVH(0) defect may be observed by electron spin magnetic resonance techniques with characteristic hyperfine satellites. A large hyperfine splitting is observable for the ^{33}S , similar to the case of SVV(-) defect (cf. Table II). However, the EPR spectra of the two defects can be readily distinguished by the hyperfine doublet of ^1H ; the hyperfine coupling is small, because the spin density has a tiny contribution from the hydrogen atom. Unlike the case of SVV(-), all the hyperfine couplings of ^{13}C ions are much smaller than those of ^{33}S , which also enables to distinguish the spectra of the two defects.

2. Sulfur-vacancy-vacancy-hydrogen complex

The SVV defect possesses multiple dangling bonds and one of them may be passivated by a mobile interstitial hydrogen in diamond. The resulting SVVH defect, shown in Fig. 11(c), has a C_{1h} symmetry. Due to multiple occupied and

FIG. 13. Spin-density distribution around the SVH defect with two different views: (a) Side and (b) top view of $(1\bar{1}0)$ plane. S and C atoms are shown by yellow and dark spheres, respectively. The hyperfine constants for the atoms labeled here are given in Table IV. Yellow and blue lobes represent a positive and negative isovalues of the calculated spin density with an isosurface value at 0.006 \AA^{-3} , respectively.

TABLE IV. Hyperfine constants (A_{xx} , A_{yy} , and A_{zz}) for the nearest-neighbor atoms for the neutral SVH defect. The atom labels are shown in Fig. 13.

Atom	A_{xx} (MHz)	A_{yy} (MHz)	A_{zz} (MHz)
S	368.9	363.3	429.8
H	6.1	0.5	12.1
C ₁	12.0	11.4	24.4
C ₂	14.0	13.5	27.8
C ₃	83.0	81.5	168.3
C ₄	76.8	75.4	155.0
C ₅	-10.35	-8.9	-13.3

empty defect levels in the band gap (Fig. 1), various charge states of SVVH occur as a function of the Fermi level (Fig. 2). The neutral charge state is dominant with the ground state $S = 1/2$ for the position of the Fermi level in the lower half of the band gap, whereas the negative charge state is dominant with a ground state $S = 1$ for the position of the Fermi level in the upper half of the band gap. The high-spin ground state is stabilized in a similar fashion as it occurred for the neutral SVV defect.

The spin density for the neutral SVVH defect is shown in Fig. 14. Because of the C_{1h} symmetry, the spin density and the hyperfine constants on the two sides of our mirror plane are identical. The majority of the spin density is localized on the carbon dangling bonds of the C₆₋₇ atoms. The hyperfine constants are listed in Table V. The spin density is significant on the C-H unit of the defect, yielding the absolute values of the hyperfine constants of ¹H close to or above 10 MHz. In the negative charge state, the spin density is mostly localized on the S atom; the largest hyperfine constants can be observed for the ³³S, which are, however, much smaller than those for the SV(-), SVV(-), or SVH(0) defects (cf. Tables I-V). The second largest hyperfine constants occur for two identical ¹³C atoms. The hyperfine coupling of ¹H is weak, yet observable, with the absolute values below 10 MHz.

H. Description of sulfur implanted diamonds

Before considering the implications of implantation, we discuss the thermal stability of the basic sulfur defects by comparing their formation energies, shown in the left panel

FIG. 14. Spin-density distribution around the core of the neutral SVVH defect with two different views: (a) Side and (b) top view of (110) plane. S and C atoms are shown by yellow and dark spheres, respectively. The hyperfine constants for the atoms labeled here are given in Table V. Yellow and blue lobes represent a positive and negative isovalues at 0.0076 \AA^{-3} of the calculated spin density, respectively.

TABLE V. Hyperfine constants (A_{xx} , A_{yy} , and A_{zz}) for the nearest-neighbor atoms for the neutral and negatively charged SVVH defects. The atom labels are shown in Fig. 14.

Atom	A_{xx} (MHz)	A_{yy} (MHz)	A_{zz} (MHz)
SVVH(0)	$S = 1/2$		
S	-106.4	-105.3	-138.7
H	17.8	8.87	-28.49
C ₁₋₂	-29.2	-25.4	-48.2
C ₃₋₄	-23.3	-22.1	-40.9
C ₅	-24.9	-24.5	-35.2
C ₆₋₇	131.8	131.0	307.1
C ₈	17.6	16.3	34.3
SVVH(-)	$S = 1$		
S	252.4	248.5	274.5
H	-6.2	5.8	8.5
C ₁₋₂	12.3	10.7	20.6
C ₃₋₄	36.4	35.8	59.8
C ₅	-9.0	-8.8	-12.2
C ₆₋₇	80.5	80.4	166.3
C ₈	3.4	3.1	9.6

of Fig. 2. Except for the p-type diamond, the SV complex evolves as the most stable defect, followed by the S_s defect. The interstitial defect has a very high formation energy and it is unlikely to occur in diamond. Indeed, the W31 EPR center, which we have associated with SV(-) defect, was observed in nitrogen-doped diamond, where the nitrogen-related deep donors may provide electrons to the SV defect. To our knowledge, the W31 EPR center is the only confirmed spectroscopical fingerprint of sulfur in diamond.

In sulfur-implanted diamond, sulfur may create several vacancies in a cascade process, and the sulfur atom may stop at the substitutional site by kicking out a carbon atom from the lattice, forming the S_s defect. After annealing, the vacancies may diffuse depending on the annealing temperature. Neutral vacancies, V(0), become mobile at temperatures around 600 °C, with an activation energy (ΔE) of 2.3 ± 0.3 eV, as determined experimentally [44], which was also largely confirmed by the HSE06 calculations [7]. For the V(-), the HSE06 diffusion activation energy of 3.5 eV was obtained [7]. The diffusion constant can be computed as follows:

$$D \approx \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta E}{k_B T}\right), \quad (5)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant and T is the temperature. By assuming the same diffusion constant for V(0) and V(-) defects in Eq. (5), it can be estimated that V(-) defects become mobile from temperatures around 800 °C.

To achieve mobile neutral vacancies, the (quasi) Fermi level is to be positioned at around $E_v + 2.0$ eV (see Table VI) that may appear in heavily implanted regions of diamond. At that Fermi level, the S_s is in the (2+) charge state and the resulting SV defect becomes neutral. Since multiple vacancies are formed during implantation, another vacancy may approach the neutral SV defect forming the neutral SVV defect.

TABLE VI. The charge transition levels of defects. Donor levels are given with respect to E_c (conduction band minimum), and acceptor levels are given with respect to E_v (valence band maximum). The data related to oxygen defects are taken from Ref. [17], whereas the data related to intrinsic and nitrogen defects are taken from Ref. [7].

Defect	Charge transition level	Energy (eV)
S_i	(2 + +)	$E_c - 3.8$
	(+ 0)	$E_c - 2.6$
S_s	(2 + +)	$E_c - 2.9$
	(+ 0)	$E_c - 1.6$
SV	(0 −)	$E_v + 4.0$
	(− 2−)	$E_v + 4.5$
SVV	(+ 0)	$E_c - 4.1$
	(0 −)	$E_v + 2.3$
	(− 2−)	$E_v + 3.9$
SH	(+ 0)	$E_c - 1.2$
SVH	(+ 0)	$E_c - 4.8$
	(0 −)	$E_v + 2.6$
SVVH	(+ 0)	$E_c - 4.8$
	(0 −)	$E_v + 2.6$
	(− 2−)	$E_v + 4.3$
H_i	(+ 0)	$E_c - 3.5$
	(0 −)	$E_v + 3.5$
	(− 2−)	$E_v + 5.0$
O_s	(2 + +)	$E_c - 4.9$
	(+ 0)	$E_c - 3.2$
	(0 −)	$E_v + 4.1$
	(− 2−)	$E_v + 5.0$
OV	(2 + +)	$E_c - 4.9$
	(+ 0)	$E_c - 3.6$
	(0 −)	$E_v + 2.9$
	(− 2−)	$E_v + 4.7$
OVH	(+ 0)	$E_c - 3.3$
	(0 −)	$E_v + 2.8$
	(− 2−)	$E_v + 4.3$
	(+ 0)	$E_c - 1.8$
N_s	(0 −)	$E_c - 3.6$
	(+ 0)	$E_c - 4.4$
NV	(0 −)	$E_v + 2.7$
	(− 2−)	$E_v + 4.9$
	(+ 0)	$E_c - 3.5$
NVH	(0 −)	$E_v + 2.4$
	(− 2−)	$E_v + 2.9$
	(+ 0)	$E_c - 4.9$
V	(+ 0)	$E_c - 4.4$
	(0 −)	$E_v + 2.0$
	(− 2−)	$E_v + 4.9$
	(+ 0)	$E_c - 4.3$
V_2	(0 −)	$E_v + 2.3$
	(− 2−)	$E_v + 3.2$

The binding energy of these defect reactions can be computed as

$$V(0) + S_s(2+) \Rightarrow SV(0) + 2h + 8.7 \text{ eV}, \quad (6)$$

$$V(0) + SV(0) \Rightarrow SVV(0) + 2.5 \text{ eV}, \quad (7)$$

where h denotes the hole, generated in the process. Equation (6) implies that the formation of SV defect is very likely when the vacancy is near S_s . On the other hand, the binding

energy in Eq. (7) between SV(0) and V(0) is close to the barrier energy of V(0), and thus SVV(0) may dissociate on annealing.

We also note that two neutral vacancies may be combined to form divacancies,

$$V(0) + V(0) \Rightarrow V_2(0) + 4.2 \text{ eV}. \quad (8)$$

These divacancies may survive the annealing process and could appear in the sulfur implanted diamonds as residual defects. On the other hand, the results imply that sulfur is preferred over the partner vacancy for the diffusing vacancies as the energy gain towards SV is much larger than that towards V_2 . Therefore, if the S_s is situated near multiple vacancies in a region of sulfur implanted diamond, then SV preferably forms over V_2 .

In the experiment [45], the sulfur implantation is carried out to CVD diamond samples with a depth of about 50 nm. In these diamond samples, it is likely that hydrogen is left in the sample, which can be activated and become mobile on annealing. The most stable sulfur-related SV defect may be combined with interstitial hydrogen, which is in turn neutral at $E_{\text{Fermi}} = E_v + 2.0 \text{ eV}$ (see right panel of Fig. 2 and Table VI). As shown in Fig. 15, the calculated binding energy for this process is 3.0 eV. Furthermore, the defect reaction between the S_s and the H_i reads as

$$S_s(2+) + H_i \Rightarrow SH(+) + h + 1.7 \text{ eV}. \quad (9)$$

This indicates that the SH defect is unstable on annealing at the temperatures when the neutral vacancies are mobile.

In the same experiment, the annealing temperature was set to 1200 °C after sulfur implantation [45] where the vacancies are definitely mobile. Our results imply that the majority of sulfur defects appear as the SV while the S_s also occurs but to a smaller extent. Furthermore, the SV may adsorb interstitial hydrogen, so that the SVH defect could also appear in CVD diamonds. Beside those defects, divacancies (or larger vacancy aggregates) also exist where few isolated vacancies could appear ejected from larger vacancy aggregates before the annealing has been stopped. The schema of sulfur implanted diamonds is depicted in the right panel of Fig. 16 as a summary.

I. NV creation in sulfur-doped diamond with nitrogen implantation

Nitrogen implantation can be used to create NV centers as single photon emitters in sulfur doped diamonds. In this case, the concentration of nitrogen is much lower than that of the dopants. During nitrogen implantation, a significant number of vacancies are created. If these vacancies remain neutral, then they tend to aggregate and form larger vacancy complexes such as V_2 defects, which may lower the efficiency of NV creation.

As shown in previous studies, the charge states of defects in diamond depend on the presence of nearby donors or acceptors [46,47]. If nitrogen is implanted relatively close to the S_s , then the latter may induce a negative charge state on two vacancies generated by nitrogen implantation. Note that the S_s cannot donate both electrons to the same vacancy since the $S_s(2+)$ and the $V(2-)$ do not share the same Fermi-level

FIG. 15. The binding energy for complex formation of SV, OV, NV, V₂, SVV, SVV, SVH, NVH, and OVH as a function of the Fermi level. We here consider charge conserving defect reactions without ejecting holes or electrons. Furthermore, constituent defect species with sharing the same sign of charge states are disregarded due to Coulomb repulsion.

region. We note that it has been demonstrated that phosphorus doping induces a negative charge on vacancies [8], where phosphorus is a single-electron donor. In this term, the S_s is more efficient as a double donor.

During annealing the mobile negatively charged vacancies do not recombine with each other but either with the N_s or the S_s. In the first case, negatively charged NV defect, i.e., the NV center is formed. In the second case, SV(-) defect is formed. It is difficult to estimate the ratio of the two processes. The binding energy for the complex formation of NV defect

is read as

$$V(0) + N_s(+) \Rightarrow NV(0) + h + 4.2 \text{ eV}, \quad (10)$$

which is significantly smaller than that for the SV formation. Nevertheless, if the vacancies are created closer to the N_s than the S_s after nitrogen implantation, then the N_s may trap the diffusing vacancy before it can combine with the S_s.

In total, sulfur doped CVD diamond mediates the formation of NV center after nitrogen implantation by the following factors: (i) SV defects trap interstitial hydrogen, therefore,

FIG. 16. Schematic diagram about sulfur-doped diamond via sulfur implantation and annealing (a) before and (b) after nitrogen implantation with annealing.

many interstitial hydrogen defects are removed prior or after nitrogen implantation and, as a consequence, the formation of NVH defects [48] (see Fig. 2) becomes less likely with keeping the NV centers intact; (ii) S_s defects are double donors that can effectively charge vacancies formed after nitrogen implantation which prevents the formation of vacancy clusters by increasing the probability to combine diffusing vacancies with N_s .

It is intriguing to analyze the photostability and spin coherence of NV center in S-doped CVD diamonds. The NV center measurements are carried out under the illumination of green light (typically, achieved with a 2.33-eV laser). To this end, the photoionization threshold energies should be studied for the most important sulfur-related defects. When the defect loses an electron in the photoionization process, the threshold energy is referenced to the conduction band minimum, whereas it is referenced to the valence band maximum for adding an electron to the defect in the photoionization process.

We start this analysis with the S_s defect. If the defect is initially in the neutral charge state, then it will rapidly transition to the (+) charge state on green illumination. In this charge state, the green light does not induce any charge flipping (see Table VI). Similarly, if the defect is in the (2+) charge state, then the green light has no effect on its charge state. As discussed above, the most likely stable charge state of the S_s is (2+), which is diamagnetic. Therefore, no spin or charge fluctuations occur due to S_s defects.

Next, we turn to the neutral SV defect, which is optically inactive because of the selection rules, making it a photostable defect. Furthermore, if the defect is in the negative charge state, then the 2.33-eV excitation converts it to neutral charge state. In either case, the SV defect remains in the nonmagnetic neutral charge state. Therefore, the SV defect provides an ideal environment for quantum optics operation of NV centers in diamond.

Additionally, we consider the SVH defect under illumination. The neutral charge state remains stable, while the negative charge state will convert to the neutral state when excited by the 2.33-eV laser. If the neutral SVH defect captures a hole, then the positive charge state will remain photostable. Hence, we conclude that the most likely configuration for the SVH defect is the neutral charge state, which has a $S = 1/2$ paramagnetic state.

The schematic diagram in Fig. 16(a) illustrates the possible processes in sulfur-doped diamond. A critical issue with sulfur doping is that the SV complex is principally more stable than the S_s , limiting the ability to fully realize the double donor nature of S_s . As a result, not all the implanted sulfur ions can contribute to the activation of NV centers, which could explain the observed 75% creation yield of NV center after nitrogen implantation of sulfur-doped diamond [45], as shown in Fig. 16(b).

Experimental results have shown that sulfur doping improves the coherence time of NV center's electron spin with respect to that of nondoped CVD diamond [45]. A reduction in coherence time is typically associated with electron spins in the lattice, generated by defects such as the V_2 . On the other hand, SV defects have a closed shell singlet ground state that is optically inactive, thus it provides an electron spin-free environment for the NV center in diamond.

J. NV creation in oxygen-doped diamonds with nitrogen implantation

In this last part, we compare the oxygen-doped and sulfur-doped CVD diamonds in terms of activation of NV centers after nitrogen implantation and annealing, given the observed NV creation yield of 68% in the oxygen-doped diamond samples [45]. To this end, we use the computational results on oxygen-related defects from our previous study [17]. The formation energies and charge transition levels of oxygen-related defects are presented in the right panel of Fig. 2, whereas the binding energies of oxygen-related defects are shown in Fig. 15.

In contrast to sulfur dopant, oxygen, as a light element, is most stable as a substitutional defect (O_s). Although the O_s has two deep donor levels, it has hyperdeep acceptor levels too, making it an amphoteric defect. The donor levels of O_s lie deeper than those of S_s . Thus, the O_s does not negatively charge nearby vacancies as efficiently as the S_s does. After oxygen ion implantation and annealing, a mobile vacancy may combine with the O_s , forming the OV defect (see Fig. 15). We assume that the OV defect may coexist with the O_s but the relative concentration between O_s and OV is much higher than that between S_s and SV.

The OV complex is also an amphoteric defect, possessing multiple donor and acceptor levels (see Table VI), where the oxygen remains at the substitutional site, exhibiting the C_{3v} symmetry. The most relevant neutral and negative charge states realize the $S = 1$ and $S = 1/2$ ground states, respectively [17]. Trapping the mobile interstitial hydrogen further leads to the formation OVH complex, which binding energy is similar to that of NVH complex (see Fig. 15). The OVH complex has both donor and acceptor levels, as well, where the neutral and negative charge states possess the $S = 1/2$ and $S = 1$ ground states, respectively [17].

We hypothesize that the beneficial effect of oxygen-doping for the creation of NV center by nitrogen implantation technique is related to the following factors:

(i) The majority of implanted oxygen ions substitutes carbon in the lattice, which can negatively charge nearby vacancies. As compared to sulfur-doped diamond, the number of O_s donors per implanted oxygen ions is higher than the respective value for the S_s . However, the doping efficiency toward vacancies is rather favored by S_s donors. Hence, the interplay of these two effects ultimately sets the probability of charging nearby vacancies, which is a crucial process in the activation of NV centers in diamond.

(ii) A fractional part of the oxygen defects appears as the OV complex. In CVD diamonds, OV complexes capture hydrogen interstitials, which decreases the probability of the formation of NVH complexes and leaves NV centers intact.

Finally, we discuss the photostability of the oxygen-related defects under the green laser. The O_s appears as neutral or single positively charged defect where the latter occurs when charging of a nearby vacancy was successful. The (+) charge state of O_s can be converted to the neutral state with ejecting a hole, which might be captured by the NV(-) defect. Then NV(0) will be converted to the NV(-) with ejecting a hole on strong green illumination. Since the O_s is neutral in this moment the capture of hole is not so likely, thus the O_s

remains neutral with $S = 0$ state. That is a photostable state because green illumination does not convert it to either (+) or (−) charge state.

The OV complex may exist in the neutral or (−) charge state after defect reactions. Both charge states are photostable on green illumination. Similarly, the OVH complex may exist in the neutral or (−) charge state after defect reactions. Both charge states are again photostable.

These results imply that oxygen doping most likely creates a photostable and electron spin-free environment toward the NV center. The most abundant O_s defects remains in the $S = 0$ ground state, whereas the less abundant oxygen vacancy-related defects are paramagnetic but also photostable. We conclude that the coherence time of the NV centers can be improved in this environment, which supports the earlier experimental findings [45].

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have studied the sulfur defects in diamond by utilizing hybrid density-functional-theory plane-wave supercell calculations. Our investigation focused on various sulfur-related defects, including interstitial sulfur, substitutional sulfur, and sulfur substitutional with vacancy as a complex defect as well as the complexes of these defects with hydrogen. We established the accurate donor and acceptor levels of these defects in diamond. We found that substitutional sulfur is not a shallow donor in diamond. Its complex with hydrogen produces a somewhat shallower donor level but it is still deep. Furthermore, the binding energy of the complex indicates that the complex can dissociate at such annealing temperatures that are typically used to remove vacancy defects in irradiated diamond. Our calculations support previous findings, which associated the W31 EPR center with the negatively charged sulfur-vacancy defect in diamond. We also found that sulfur-vacancy complex can effectively trap mobile interstitial hydrogen in diamond, forming a sulfur-vacancy-hydrogen complex.

We analyzed the possible defect species in sulfur ion implanted and annealed diamond. We concluded that the formation of sulfur-vacancy complex is more likely than that of substitutional sulfur and the sulfur-vacancy complex may trap hydrogen in shallow CVD diamond layers. Implanting nitrogen ions into these sulfur-doped diamonds can facilitate the formation of the nitrogen-vacancy center by the double donor

nature of the substitutional sulfur and trapping of hydrogen by the sulfur-vacancy complex. We find that sulfur defects are photostable and provide electron spin-free environment toward the nitrogen-vacancy center, which can principally improve the coherence time of the nitrogen-vacancy center's electron spin. We carried out the same analysis for the oxygen-doped CVD diamond layers by taking our previous *ab initio* data. We find some subtle differences in the mediation of nitrogen-vacancy defect creation by the two dopants. Direct estimation of the creation yield of the nitrogen-vacancy center in sulfur or oxygen-doped diamond is not feasible from the dataset we have, and it is beyond the scope of this study. Nevertheless, our calculations provide atomistic insights about the doped layers and could support the improvement in the creation yield and the electron spin coherence times in these doped diamond layers. Our results imply that the creation yield of nitrogen-vacancy center in sulfur-doped diamond might be improved by careful engineering of the annealing parameters after sulfur implantation, in order to avoid complex formation of substitutional sulfur and the vacancy. This is extremely challenging because substitutional sulfur is less stable than sulfur-vacancy complex but it might be possible to freeze the sulfur defects in their metastable state and simultaneously heal the crystalline damages created by irradiation.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The data supporting this study's findings are available within the article.

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